

CREAF

OPEN SCIENCE

GLOSSARY

2025

SHAPING THE FUTURE OF SCIENCE: OPEN,
COLLABORATIVE, AND INTEGRITY-DRIVEN

This Glossary is a dynamic resource that provides clear definitions and explanations of terms related to Open Science, supporting its implementation at CREAM.

CREAF OPEN SCIENCE GLOSSARY

This Glossary is a living resource for terms and definitions related to Open Science. It will be updated regularly to adapt to the evolving research landscape.

Cerdanyola del Vallès, 2025

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INTRODUCTION

As CREAM continues to promote Open Science, it is essential to ensure that all stakeholders have a shared understanding of key concepts and terminology in the evolving research landscape. This Glossary is a dynamic and evolving resource, providing clear definitions and explanations of terms related to Open Science. It is designed to support the implementation of the CREAM Open Science Policy (CREAF, 2025) and other institutional regulations. In addition to addressing policy-specific terminology, the Glossary encompasses broader concepts that shape research practices, fostering a culture of openness, collaboration, and integrity throughout the entire research lifecycle.

The glossary is intended for researchers, research managers and administrators, and anyone interested in understanding and advancing responsible research practices at CREAM and beyond.

Further open scholarship terms can be found in FORRT's Glossary (Parsons et al., 2022).

GLOSSARY

A

Academic extractivism refers to the practice where researchers, typically from more affluent countries —often in the Global North—, extract data, knowledge, or resources from low- and middle-income regions —often in the Global South— without providing adequate benefits or recognition to local communities and researchers.

Academic freedom is the right of scholars to pursue knowledge and conduct research without undue interference, operating within professional, ethical and legal boundaries. It includes but is not limited to: the freedom to choose research topics and methodologies, publish findings, analyse data without external pressure, be protected from censorship or retaliation for controversial ideas, and teaching in the classroom. However, this freedom is not absolute; researchers must adhere to ethical and integrity standards, comply with laws regarding defamation, obscenity, and intellectual property, and align with institutional policies and disciplinary norms. Additionally, researchers remain accountable to funding bodies and must follow grant requirements.

Accessibility is the degree to which research outputs can be easily discovered, retrieved, and used by systems or a diverse range of users, regardless of their abilities, technical expertise, or institutional affiliations. Access can be open, closed/restricted, or embargoed (See **Openness**, **FAIR**, and **Paywall**).

Aggregators collect and provide access to full-text content from various sources, making it accessible through a single platform. They may also offer indexing functionality to make the content searchable (See **Indexing Services**). Examples include [OpenAlex](#) –database of open access and paywalled scholarly outputs such as journal articles and datasets– and [CORE](#) –database of open access journal articles.

Article Processing Charges (APCs) are fees charged by some academic publishers to authors or their institutions to cover the costs associated with publishing an open access article, shifting the costs from readers/subscribers ("pay to read") to authors/institutions ("pay to publish"). APCs may range from around 1,000€ to 5,000€ or more per article, and are paid after acceptance (See **Submission Processing Charges**).

Attribution is the act of giving credit to the original creator or source of information, ideas, or content used in a work. It involves acknowledging the contributions of others by identifying the source, typically including details like the author's name, title of the work, and other relevant information. While similar to citation, attribution is often broader in scope and can be less formal, ranging from formal academic citations to acknowledgments.

Author addendum: Contract modification that helps researchers protect their publication rights, enabling them to share, teach, and build upon their work while navigating standard publishing agreements (See **Copyright Transfer Agreements**).

B

Blockchain Technology (BCT) is a secure and transparent way to record information. Each piece of information is stored in "blocks," which are linked together in a chronological order, creating a chain. This ensures that once data is recorded, it cannot be altered without everyone noticing. In research, BCT may help meet legal and ethical standards and support the FAIR principles, ensuring the integrity, confidentiality, and authentication of data, preventing falsification and misuse.

Bibliodiversity is the variety of publishing models, platforms, and formats that support diverse research outputs. By accommodating different research outputs, languages, workflows, and topics, bibliodiversity supports inclusivity, reduces bias, and fosters global collaboration in scholarly communication.

C

CERIF is a data model and standard format for managing and exchanging research information used to facilitate the interoperability and exchange of research information between different systems and organizations.

Cherry-picking refers to the selective practice of choosing data or evidence that supports a particular hypothesis or viewpoint while ignoring contradictory information (See **Screen-picking**).

Closed or restricted access refers to research outputs that are not freely available to the public, but behind a paywall, a datawall, available upon request (subject to specific criteria or permissions), or institutional login requirements (See **Embargo**).

Collective work is a compilation that includes contributions from multiple authors, each of which constitutes a separate and independent work, assembled into a cohesive whole under the direction of a single entity or individual.

Computational reproducibility is the ability to produce the same results using the original data, code, and computational methods from a study. It requires open data, open code and appropriate documentation.

Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) is a standardized system used for accurate representation of the roles and contributions of individuals involved in research projects. There are up to 14 distinct contributor roles, including conceptualization, funding acquisition, or data curation. CRediT information can be captured in a machine-readable format, facilitating easier tracking and analysis of contributions across research projects.

Copyright Transfer Agreements (CTA) are legally binding contracts where authors transfer exclusive rights to publish, distribute, and sell their work to a publisher. CTAs often restrict authors' ability to freely share their work, limiting self-archiving, reuse for teaching, and future publications. This can create barriers to open science initiatives by impeding unrestricted access and distribution of research (See **Secondary Publishing Rights**).

Creative Commons are a set of standardized copyright licenses that allow researchers and content creators to easily share their work while retaining some control over how it is used. Authors can choose from several CC license options, allowing them to specify which rights they want to reserve and which they want to grant to others (See **Intellectual property**).

Current Research Information Systems (CRIS), RIS or RIMS are information systems designed to store, manage, and exchange research information related to research activities, with core entities such as people, organizations, projects, and outputs. They can be institutional, funder-operated, regional, national, or supranational. CRIS systems are used in research reporting and assessment, and to support and enable Open Science: they store linked metadata about research projects and their outputs and researchers, enable the discovery of potential collaborators based on research interests and activities, can integrate with institutional repositories to facilitate the deposit of OA versions of outputs, offer public-facing interfaces that showcase institutional research activities, outputs and researcher profiles, help monitor

compliance with funder and institutional OS mandates, serve as a centralized research information repository to allow for efficient organization and retrieval of knowledge.

D

Datawall involves exchanging personal data for access to content rather than paying a monetary fee (See **Paywall**).

Data management plans (DMP) are documents that describe how researchers will handle data during and after a research project to ensure data integrity, reproducibility, and FAIR principles, improving research efficiency and organization. A DMP typically includes description of data to be collected or generated, methodologies and standards for data collection and processing, plans for data storage, backup, and security, strategies for data sharing, and ethical considerations.

Data ownership is the designation of authority and responsibility over research data. In Open Science, data ownership is often viewed more as stewardship rather than exclusive possession. Researchers and institutions are seen as custodians of data, responsible for its proper management, quality, and accessibility. This approach emphasizes accountability –ensuring data accuracy, integrity, and compliance with ethical and legal standards–, accessibility –making data available to the wider scientific community and public when appropriate–, and preservation –maintaining data in usable formats for long-term access and reuse.

Data sharing agreement (DSA): Formal contract between two or more parties outlining their roles, the data to be shared, permitted uses, access conditions, restrictions, confidentiality, security measures, and compliance with legal and ethical standards.

Double dipping refers to a practice where publishers receive payment twice for the same content: once for subscriptions to read and again for APCs to make their articles OA in those same subscription journals. This practice is common in hybrid OA journals, where some articles are OA while others remain behind a paywall.

E

Embargo: Access restriction for a particular time applied to an output: articles, data, unpublished works (e.g., theses, patents). It represents a temporary form of restricted access that eventually transitions to open access.

- **Publication embargo:** Delays before Green OA content becomes freely available, with an average of 12 months for STEM subjects and 24 for humanities and social sciences.
- **Press embargo:** Request for journalists to wait until the publication date before publicly covering the publication, which might apply to the full text, the metadata or the abstract. This allows publishers to provide a paper to journalists a few days in advance, so they have time to prepare their stories.

F

FAIR represents a set of guiding principles —not a one-size-fits-all technical standard— for data management, ensuring that it can be easily shared, understood, and built upon by other researchers, fostering collaboration and accelerating scientific progress. FAIR data should be easily discoverable, accessible, integrated with other data and work across different applications or workflows, and be well-described to allow proper reuse and replication.

File drawer problem refers to a situation where many research studies with null or negative findings remain unpublished, metaphorically tucked away in researchers' "file drawers", perhaps because researchers thought those effects were unlikely to be published or they had tried to publish them and failed.

G

Global intellectual heritage is humanity's collective intellectual and cultural achievements throughout history. It's a shared global resource that should be preserved and made accessible

for all, across geographic and socioeconomic boundaries. Open Science contributes to humankind's intellectual legacy.

H

HARKing (Hypothesizing After Results are Known) is the bad practice of presenting post-hoc hypotheses as if they were a priori predictions and suppressing a priori hypotheses that were not confirmed by the results, which can inflate false positive rates (See **Cherry-Picking**).

I

Inappropriate authorship violates ethical standards by misrepresenting contributions, which undermines research integrity, distorts credit attribution, and leads to disputes or unfair career advantages. It can take several forms:

- **Adding non-contributing authors** through coercion —often by seniors—, to gain favour, prestige or enhance credibility (honorary/guest authorship), or reciprocity (swap authorship).
- **Misappropriating credit:** Claiming authorship of others' work (theft authorship), often involving plagiarism, i.e., copying text or ideas without proper attribution.
- **Manipulating author order:** Misrepresenting levels of contribution to inflate someone's perceived contribution or to downplay others' roles.
- **Omitting significant contributors**, often to hide conflicts of interest (ghost authorship).

Indexing services are searchable databases of bibliographic metadata from academic publications, including titles, authors, abstracts, citations, subject areas and disciplines. These services allow users to search across multiple fields to discover relevant works, and some may also provide citation tracking and journal quality metrics. While they typically don't host full content, they provide a link to the source (See Aggregators). Examples include Web of Science and Scopus and the open alternative DOAJ.

Intellectual property (IP) refers to the legal rights granted to the creators of original works, such as inventions, literary and artistic works, designs, and symbols, names, and images used in commerce. These rights ensure creators have control over the use and distribution of their works.

Interoperability ensures that different systems, platforms, and data formats can work together seamlessly. It encompasses two key aspects:

- **Technological interoperability** enables systems to connect and exchange data through common protocols, standards, and data formats. It deals with the syntax and structure of data exchange.
- **Semantic interoperability** ensures that the meaning and context of the exchanged data are preserved and understood by all systems, using standardized vocabularies and metadata. It deals with the meaning and context of the data.

K

Knowledge management (KM) is the process of capturing, organizing, preserving, and sharing all forms of knowledge. In research, KM encompasses explicit knowledge (publications, data, research outputs), tacit knowledge (held by staff), and best practices. KM transforms individual and collective knowledge into usable assets, facilitates collaboration, and enables timely access to information for decision-making. Effective KM integrates RDM, RIM, and knowledge repositories to support open scientific practices.

M

Machine-readable refers to data or files that can be easily processed by computers. These formats use standardized structures and metadata, making it easier to find, validate, and analyse information. Machine-readable formats can support assistive technologies used by both individuals with disabilities and neurodiverse individuals. Examples include CSV, JSON, and certain PDFs –those with searchable and selectable text, not image-only.

Metadata are the descriptors used for describing, tracing, use and management of the deposited item (e.g., title, authors, institutional affiliation, keywords, etc.).

Metascience (also known as ‘research on research’ or ‘the science of science’) uses scientific methodology to study research itself: its practices, processes, and outcomes. It aims to diagnose issues like reproducibility and bias in research, while providing empirical, comprehensive evidence for reforms (See **Scientometrics**). Metascience supports and critically examines open science initiatives, evaluating their effectiveness in addressing systemic problems and monitoring for unintended consequences.

O

Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (ORRI) is a governance approach that fosters collaboration among researchers, innovators, policymakers, citizens and other societal actors to align research and technological development with societal values and needs. It integrates principles of openness, mutual responsibility, diversity, and sustainability into research and innovation processes.

Open access (OA): OA refers to the unrestricted online availability of the full texts of research publications combined with the rights to use these outputs fully –OA to research data is often governed by different frameworks (See **Open data**). There are two main pathways to achieve OA publications:

1. **Gold Route:** It involves making articles openly accessible through the publisher's platform. There are several models:
 - **Diamond/platinum:** Articles published in fully OA journals or platforms with no fees for readers or authors. The publishing costs are covered by other means.
 - **Fully Gold:** Articles published in fully OA journals, where all content is freely available immediately upon publication. Gold OA journals typically charge APCs to cover publishing costs.
 - **Subscribe to Open (S2O)** allows journals to transition from subscription-based access to OA based on library subscriptions and not APCs. If enough libraries renew their subscriptions, the journal's content for that year becomes OA.

- **Hybrid:** Subscription journals offering an OA option for individual articles upon payment of an APC. These journals contain both open and closed access content, leading to 'double-dipping.'
 - **Bronze:** Articles freely accessible on the publisher's website but without an explicit open license. For this reason, bronze OA articles cannot be legally redistributed or reused without explicit permission, falling short of the full definition of OA. Also, free access can potentially be revoked at any time.
2. **Green Route:** It involves authors self-archiving their work in OA repositories. Depending on the conditions, they can self-archive:
- **Version of Record (VoR):** The final and published version of a peer-reviewed research article that contains all copyediting changes and final formatting. It often includes additional features like downloadable citation details, article-level metrics, and links to corrections or commentaries.
 - **Author Accepted Manuscript (AAM) or postprint:** The accepted peer-reviewed version prior to publisher copyediting, typesetting, and formatting.
 - **Submitted version or preprint:** The complete version of a scholarly manuscript that has been openly shared but has not been peer-reviewed. It aims to disseminate research findings quickly and sharing null results or other findings that may be difficult to publish in traditional journals, get early feedback from peers, establish priority of scientific discoveries, and increase visibility and potential citations. It is often hosted on preprint servers and becomes a permanent, citable part of the scientific record.
 - **Working paper:** A preliminary version of a scholarly manuscript –ranging from early drafts to nearly finished manuscripts– that has not been peer-reviewed. It is shared with peers to request feedback and improve the quality of the research before formal submission to a journal. Unlike preprints, working papers are not assigned a DOI and can be easily withdrawn or updated, offering more flexibility to authors.

Open citations are open bibliographic references that link a citing source to a cited source, recognizing the contributions of the cited author(s). They can encompass scholarly publications, blog posts, datasets, and other authored works. A bibliographic citation is considered an open citation when it is structured in machine-readable formats, separate from the source, and freely

accessible. Both citing and cited entities must be identifiable with Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) and include basic metadata. Open citations can be used by scientometrics to analyse the academic impact of paywalled works without requiring access to subscription-based databases. Also, with open citations researchers from various fields can discover relevant studies more easily, facilitating collaboration across disciplines.

Open data refers to freely available, machine-readable data that can be accessed, used, modified, and shared by anyone. Open research data is essential for verifying scientific claims, fostering collaboration across disciplines, and enabling innovative applications of existing datasets.

Open knowledge is an ecosystem of open initiatives that collectively enhance transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in research and education. This includes open software, open source, open hardware, open access, open data, and open educational resources –outputs that are typically available for use, modification, and distribution under certain conditions (See Openness).

Open peer review refers to a transparent scholarly review mechanism that may include any of the following practices, either alone or in combination: publishing peer reviews, open commenting from the wider community, open discussion between authors, editors and reviewers, open review before publication through preprint, post-publication commenting, sharing author or reviewer identities, and decoupling the peer review process from the publication process.

Open Science refers to the broader cultural shift and collective efforts to make scientific research more transparent, collaborative, and accessible to all levels of an inquisitive society. It is a collective action involving coordinated efforts by multiple stakeholders (researchers, RPOs, funders, policymakers, publishers, etc.), and provides the broader context and infrastructure for change beyond individual research practices.

Open science commons encompass shared resources that enable Open Science practices, including e-infrastructure, scientific equipment and facilities, research datasets and outputs, and knowledge (expertise, methodologies, and collaborative networks). These commons typically feature digital repositories, open-source software, shared research infrastructures, collaborative online platforms for knowledge exchange, and publications, data, notebooks, etc. Two examples are ESOC —which aims to create a federated ecosystem of research data infrastructures and services—, and ORE, —a scholarly publishing service for grantees of the EC’s Framework programmes.

Open Science mindset is a personal commitment to Open Science principles in all research activities from inception to dissemination rather than being an afterthought. It is an individual's attitude in their day-to-day work that involves proactive dissemination and promotion. The mindset is crucial for driving adoption of open practices at the grassroots level.

Open source refers to software with accessible source code —not necessarily for free—, allowing users to customize and adapt it according to their needs without any licensing violation burden. It promotes flexibility and innovation through shared contributions (community development). In Open Science, open source code is the backbone of open science infrastructure, powering repositories, data-sharing platforms, and collaborative tools essential for transparent and reproducible research.

Openness refers to the principle of providing unrestricted, public, and free access to information, data, research outputs, software, educational resources, methods, and other intellectual content. It encompasses not only access but also the rights to use, modify, and redistribute these resources. In this sense, the degree of openness can vary significantly based on the terms of any applicable licence, ranging from works in the public domain with no restrictions, to permissive licences with minimal conditions (like attribution or share-alike clauses), to more restrictive licenses that may prohibit derivative works or commercialization. Additional factors affecting openness include timing of release (immediate upon publication or embargoed), format suitability for reuse, availability of necessary tools or software, clarity of documentation, language barriers, and accessibility for people with disabilities and neurodiversity.

Overlay journals are OA academic venues that select, curate, and peer-review scholarly content already hosted on external repositories or preprint servers, combining the gold and green routes to OA. After formal acceptance, authors upload their final articles, and the overlay journal links to these articles, adding publication details.

P

Papermilling: The unethical business of producing and selling scientific manuscripts and authorship positions to researchers so that they can quickly publish papers or gain authorship credits, often to meet publication requirements for career advancement. Papers from mills are usually of low quality, often exhibit fabricated or manipulated data, plagiarized content, and fake or hard-to-trace authors. They are often published in predatory journals, with lower standards for

acceptance and peer review, but they can also appear in legitimate ones, compromising trust in published research (See **Predatory journals**).

Patent mills are organizations that produce and sell absurd design registrations —not actual patents— to researchers seeking to artificially enhance their academic profiles. Unlike patents, design registrations aren't examined for novelty or uniqueness, leading to quick approvals.

Paywalls are digital barriers to academic research and scientific publications, typically requiring a subscription fee or one-time payment to view the full content.

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are unique, long-lasting digital references designed to identify and enable accurate citation, discovery, permanent access, and linking of entities in the research ecosystem. They cover research outputs, researchers, RPOs, RFOs, grants, etc., and support FAIR principles in scientific research. Some common PIDs are:

- DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for research outputs.
- Grant ID for specific grants or awards.
- OCI (Open Citation Identifier), for bibliographic citations.
- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID) for researchers.
- RAiD (Research Activity Identifier) for research projects.
- ROR (Research Organization Registry) ID for institutions –RPOs, RFOs, etc.

Predatory journals exploit the OA publishing model by charging APCs without providing legitimate editorial and publishing services. They falsely claim to be rigorous when peer-review is superficial, conducted by unqualified reviewers or not actually performed. Predatory publishers often imitate reputable ones and constantly adapt their methods to appear more legitimate.

Publish-Review-Curate (PRC) is an emerging model to scholarly communication that makes preprints, reviews, and commentaries openly available. The process, which has been endorsed by the initiative Peer Community In (PCI) and the publishing platform Open Research Europe,

typically involves three key stages: (1) **PUBLISH**: Research is published as a preprint, (2) **REVIEW**: The work undergoes peer review, resulting in transparent review reports, and (3) **CURATE**: The outputs are tagged, summarized or compiled into thematic collections, often accompanied by an editorial assessment that validates the work (See **Overlay journals**). Under the PRC model, a research output can be curated by multiple entities simultaneously, allowing for diverse forms and purposes of curation.

Publish for Purpose emphasizes the importance of meaningful and influential research over sheer quantity of publications, contrasting with the "Publish or Perish" paradigm: quality over quantity, long-term thinking, alignment with personal and professional goals, etc.

Publish or Perish is an academic culture that prioritizes frequent publication in prestigious, high-impact academic journals as the key measure of success. This mentality often values quantity over quality, compromising research integrity. It creates intense pressure on scholars to publish extensively for prestige, career advancement, funding opportunities, and job security.

Q

Questionable research practices or "sloppy science" violates traditional research values and may result from ignorance, misunderstanding, bias, or carelessness rather than intentional deception. Examples: poor data management or record-keeping, mild selective reporting of results emphasizing positive findings, poor methodology, etc. (See **Research misconduct**).

R

Replicability involves verifying a study through a combination of new data and the original method, new data and new methods, or the original data and new methods. It is meant to assess whether findings can be generalized beyond the original study, and refine methods (See **Reproducibility**).

Repositories are online platforms that collect, preserve, and allows access to the results of academic and scientific research. They organize various types of outputs —such as articles, datasets, theses, and multimedia— using structured metadata and tagging systems. This enables efficient access and discoverability while ensuring compliance with open access

mandates. They often incorporate search engine optimization (SEO) strategies to enhance visibility in online search results, and may be aggregated, making it easier for researchers and the public to find relevant work. Repositories may feature project-specific collections to enhance visibility for individual research initiatives, facilitating knowledge sharing and collaboration within the academic community.

- **Trusted repositories** meet quality standards —FAIR principles, EOSC technical specifications, CoreTrust Seal, OpenAIRE compatibility, transparent repository policy.
- **Shadow libraries** are ‘pirate’ repositories that illegally distribute copyrighted content, such as academic papers, for free by bypassing paywalls and copyright restrictions.

Reproducibility refers to the ability to obtain consistent results by re-analyzing original data with the same methods, verifying the original analysis's correctness and transparency. (See **Replicability**).

Research data is the data used to validate the results presented in scientific publications or other data used during a project that should be described in a DMP, including: statistics, results of experiments, observations, interview recordings, images, etc. While research data can exist in non-digital forms (e.g., samples, cores, living organisms, artifacts, etc.), the trend towards digitalization in research and the requirements for data sharing often lead to research data being stored and shared in digital formats (digital copies, metadata) to facilitate data management (See **Open data**).

Research data management (RDM) involves planning, documenting, preserving, and sharing research data. RDM roles can be distributed across strategy, governance, and operations to ensure comprehensive management of research data and information (See **Research information management**):

- **Strategic oversight:** Chief data officers (CDO) develop overall data strategy aligned with Open Science principles, ensure compliance with data policies and regulations, identify opportunities for data sharing and collaboration, and coordinate with external stakeholders and funding bodies.
- **Governance:** Data stewards implement policies and standards, assist with DMPs and code management, help researchers to comply with FAIR principles

and make their data "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," advise on data organization, storage, and backup strategies, support data preservation and archiving, bridge communication between researchers and IT/data infrastructure, and may assume some Database Administrator (DBA) responsibilities.

- **Data handling:** Data curators manage data throughout its lifecycle within research projects, clean and standardize raw data, detect and correct errors, prepare data for sharing and preservation, and create and maintain documentation and detailed metadata.
- **Technical infrastructure:** Data architects design and implement the organization's data infrastructure, and ensure systems support open science practices and data sharing.
- **Analytical capabilities:** Data scientists perform advanced data analysis and modelling, create data visualizations, and support researchers with analytical needs.

Research ethics and integrity are crucial for maintaining trust in research and ensuring its quality and reliability:

- **Research ethics** are the principles and guidelines that govern the conduct of research to contribute to research integrity. It is primarily concerned with ensuring the rights, safety, dignity and well-being of people, the humane treatment of animals, and considering the environmental consequences of research activities and protecting ecosystems. Research ethics should be overseen by research ethics committees.
- **Research integrity** refers to the behaviour and practices of researchers in applying ethical principles, encompassing the entire research process from planning to dissemination. It is a continuously developing concept, including issues like data management, authorship, reporting of results, mentoring and supervision, promotion practices, among others. Research integrity is primarily the responsibility of researchers themselves (See **Research misconduct**).

Research information is metadata about research activities and outputs on researchers and their affiliations, publications and other research outputs, projects and funding, research equipment and facilities, etc.

Research information management (RIM) deals with collecting, tracking, and curating research information to support discovery and reuse of research outputs. RIM systems like Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) help institutions manage this information in a centralized manner.

Research misconduct is fabrication, falsification, or plagiarism in proposing, performing, or reviewing research, or in reporting research results. It involves deliberate deception. Examples: salami slicing, fabricating data to secure funding or publications, manipulating images, severe selective reporting of results—completely omitting negative results—, plagiarizing text or ideas, falsifying credentials or qualifications, inappropriate authorship, misusing research funds for personal expenses, excessive self-citation as a form of citation manipulation or to artificially inflate an author's citation metrics, etc. (See **Questionable research practices**).

S

Salami slicing is the practice of splitting a single research study and the argument that should collectively form one publication into multiple publications or ‘slices’. It artificially inflates an author's publication record without producing genuinely new findings.

Science diplomacy is a discipline that combines science, technology and international relations to meet global agendas, increase prosperity and promote understanding between countries, regions and societies. It encompasses these aspects:

- **Diplomacy for science:** Facilitating international scientific cooperation through agreements and partnerships.
- **Science for diplomacy:** Utilizing scientific collaboration as a tool for improving diplomatic relations.
- **Science in diplomacy:** Applying scientific knowledge to inform and guide foreign policy decisions. Science in diplomacy also helps manage transboundary resources and global commons and govern international shared spaces.

- **Anticipatory science diplomacy:** Developing legal frameworks to regulate the potential benefits and risks of scientific and technological breakthroughs before they become readily available.

Scientometrics is a specialized tool within the broader framework of metascience and a subfield of information science devoted to the quantitative analysis of scientific activities. Aimed at understanding research dynamics and academic impacts, Scientometrics examines subjects such as publications and citations, datasets, funding, etc. It investigates aspects such as publication trends, keyword usage to identify emerging research areas, citation patterns to assess influence, and contributions from leading authors and institutions. Additionally, it explores regional leadership in specific fields, the influence of academic journals and funding on research priorities, and shifts in methodologies (See **Metascience**).

Screen-Picking refers to the selective practice of dismissing findings to narrow down large sample sets. Screen-picking can be driven by a desire to confirm expected outcomes — dismissing data that contradict expected outcomes or research questions—, but it can also be a legitimate practice —like for quality assurance checks— if it adheres to certain principles, including but not limited to predefined criteria and documentation of all samples, including those not selected.

Secondary publishing rights (SPR) enable researchers and their institutions to reuse a work after initial publication, regardless of publishing agreement restrictions, thus eliminating the need to negotiate retained rights. SPR preserves public access without limiting primary publication venues, thus supporting the Green OA route. Typically enacted through national legislation, SPR varies by country—some impose embargo periods, while others consider immediate access.

Slow science: Movement advocating for a more deliberate and methodical approach to scientific research, opposing the fast-paced demands often imposed by academic and funding pressures. It emphasizes that quality research requires time, reflection, and a focus on thoroughness rather than speed. It critiques the "publish or perish" mentality.

Submission Processing Charges (SPC), also known as Submission Fees, are fees charged by some academic journals when authors submit their manuscripts for consideration, regardless of whether the article is ultimately accepted or rejected.

Suitable or Trusted refers to practices, tools, and methodologies that meet specific standards of quality, trustworthiness, ethics and accessibility.

T

Taxonomy is a classification system for organizing knowledge into groups that share similar characteristics, with parent/child relationships between the terms (e.g. the ORRI taxonomy). Ontologies extend taxonomies, and they can be thought of more like a web of networks, with many different types of relationships between concepts.

Transformative agreements are contracts between well-funded academic institutions, such as universities, and publishers to aggregate journal subscriptions expenses and OA publishing costs in hybrid journals for an institution's authors, both to contain the APC inflation and simplify budget management. However, there are still annual price increases and institutions are perpetually engaged in costly negotiations with no clear end in sight.

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